

seedlings were transplanted at 15-cm spacing. Water rose at 2-3 cm/d to a maximum water depth of 112 cm. Neither species had superior yield, but *O. glaberrima* showed more vigorous vegetative growth. □

Varietal differences in milled quality of rice harvested at different maturities

A. C. Roy and J. B. Fokou, IRA-Dschang, P.O. Box 44, Dschang; and S. B. C. Wanki, Upper Nun Valley Development Authority (UNVDA), P.O. Box 25, Ndop Plain, Cameroon

Rice varieties differ in grain form, milling outturn, and market price. Harvesting at different stages of maturity also affects head rice outturn and grain breakage.

Preliminary farm surveys during the 1986 crop season showed that most farmers in the Upper Nun Valley do not follow recommended practices for time of harvest. Many leave their crops in the field after maturity, harvesting when they have time. Rice harvested at different maturity stages mills out with high percentage broken and very low percentage head rice.

We grew four promising varieties and lines in nonreplicated large plots (500 m²) at Bamunka Rice Research Station, Ndop Plain, and harvested 100 m² subplots at intervals of 5 d, from 35 d after heading (DH) to 60 DH. The yields (20-40 kg rough rice/sample) were sun-dried to about 12-14% moisture, hulled, and polished using a Satake rubber roll rice mill (model SB 100). Percentages brown rice, head rice, broken rice, and marketable rice were taken for each sample. (Head rice is defined as whole milled rice, marketable rice as grains 50-100% as long as whole milled rice.) Estimated 1,000-grain weights of rough rice and brown rice also were noted for each harvest date.

Total brown and clean milled rice varied with varieties, from 73.8 to 81.7% brown rice and 63.5 to 71.3% clean milled rice, but were not markedly affected by harvest date (see table).

Effect of harvesting rice at different stages of maturity on milling outturns. Ndop Plain, Cameroon, 1987 wet season.

Variety or line	Harvest date (DH) ^a	Rough rice moisture at harvest (%)	Percent of rough rice			
			Brown rice	Clean rice	Head ^b rice	Marketable rice ^c
RNR29692	35	27.6	73.8	66.4	58.7	64.1
	40	27.1	75.5	69.5	58.3	67.6
	45	22.0	79.3	68.5	57.5	65.6
	50	20.0	79.0	65.8	35.6	60.4
	55	18.0	81.0	69.1	46.9	65.8
IR7167-33-2-3	40	30.4	81.3	71.1	42.1	68.5
	45	26.5	77.7	71.3	30.0	66.7
	50	24.5	77.1	67.5	19.9	61.6
	55	22.5	79.5	66.2	8.7	55.9
	60	12.8	80.1	71.2	10.0	63.0
B29838-SR-51-2-1	40	29.4	80.5	63.5	23.2	53.2
	45	26.5	79.2	68.9	33.5	59.0
	50	24.4	75.7	64.9	13.8	50.3
	55	22.5	78.6	67.8	14.5	52.3
	60	14.1	77.7	65.5	5.1	45.0
B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1	35	30.9	75.7	62.7	16.5	40.2
	40	29.4	74.0	66.2	13.1	51.0
	45	26.5	77.4	67.0	19.2	56.8
	50	24.5	81.2	63.2	14.3	46.5
	55	18.7	77.1	68.7	7.1	55.2
60	11.5	81.7	67.3	3.7	44.9	

^a DH = days after heading. ^b Head rice = % whole milled rice. ^c marketable rice = 50% or more than the length of whole milled rice.

RNR29692 had the highest (51.4%) and B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1 the lowest (12.3%) head rice.

Grain maturity stage profoundly affected percentage broken. Harvest more than 45 DH resulted in very high percentage broken.

Extremely high, percentage broken in all varieties (except RNR29692) harvested 40 DH and later tend to limit their adaptability as commercial varieties.

RNR29692 yielded higher than IR7167-33-2-3 at Ndop Plain. Both lines have medium-long grain with high amylose content (28.3%); B2161-C-MR-57-1-3-1 and B29838-SR-51-2-1 have medium-long grain with intermediate amylose content (23.7%). Because of its high head rice percentage, RNR29692 is under consideration for release as a commercial variety, subject to local consumer acceptance and other qualities. □

Effect on yield of cutting deepwater rice for herbage

S. K. Bardhan Roy, B. Banerji, C. Kundu, and B. K. Mandal, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

During the 1988 wet season, we cut leaves of variety CN705-18 (CN645/ Mahsuri) at different growth stages. The first cutting of the 10 May direct seeded crop was done 110 d after seeding in two plots. A second cutting was done 130 d after seeding

(immediately before panicle initiation) in only one plot. Water level at cutting was 50-60 cm (maximum water level 90 cm was in late June). Only leaves above the water were cut, leaving 5 cm of leaves intact.

Foliage yield, grain yield, and yield components were measured. The first cut in plot A produced 3.8 t green leaves/ha and in plot B, 3.6 t green leaves/ha. The second cut in plot B only 20 d after the first cut produced 3.4 t green leaves/ha (Table 1). Grain yields in single cut and uncut crops were

Table 1. Foliage and grain yield from CN705-18. Chinsurah, India, 1988.

Parameter	Control (no cut)	1 cut	2 cuts
Foliage yield (t/ha)			
1st cut	—	3.8	3.6
2d cut	—	—	3.4
At harvest	2.1	1.9	2.0
Total	2.1	5.7	9.0
Grain yield (t/ha)	1.0	1.1	1.4
Days to 50% flowering	171	175	167

similar. Yields in the double cut crop were higher. Flowering was early in the double cut crop, followed by the normal crop and by the single cut crop.

Number of effective tillers at harvest was significantly higher in the double cut crop and 1,000-grain weight

Table 2. Effect of leaf cutting on yield components. Chinsurah, India.

Character	Treatment			Percent increase or decrease over control
	No cut	1 cut	2 cuts	
Plant ht (cm)	205.0	200.0	182.0	- 11
Effective tillers at harvest (no.)	6.0	10.0	12.0	+100
Panicle length (cm)	23.4	22.0	22.5	- 4
Total grains per panicle	202.0	185.0	156.0	- 23
1000-grain wt	24.1	24.3	25.4	+ 5
Percent of sterile grains/panicle	1.9	3.6	4.2	-
Yield per plant (gm)	28.0	41.0	45.0	+ 61
Grain-to-straw ratio	0.5	0.5	0.7	-

increased slightly. Grain yield/plant and grain-to-straw ratio also increased. Plant height, total grains/panicle, and length of panicle were reduced (Table 2).

The increased number of effective tillers contributed 61% of the yield increase. The shorter plant height

contributed to better grain filling.

This preliminary study shows that herbage production is possible with photoperiod-sensitive deepwater rice, without sacrificing grain yield. □

Improving rice yield using hydrocortisone spray

K. Manian, R. Govindarasu, P. Sivasubramanian, and N. Natarajaratnam, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru College of Agriculture, Karaikal 609605, Union Territory of Pondicherry, India

The effect of hydrocortisone, a glucocorticoid hormone of higher animals, has been found to be beneficial for germination of rice. We assessed the effect of hydrocortisone on dry matter production, grain yield, and harvest index.

Hydrocortisone (50 ppm) was sprayed at different growth stages—active tillering phase (50 d after sowing [DAS]), flowering (75 DAS), and grain filling (100 DAS)—of a standing crop of IR20 at Karaikal. Spraying at flowering significantly improved grain yield and increased dry matter production (see table). Dry matter production increased most with spray at active tillering phase, but yield increased only 12%.

This trend suggests that dry matter production is stimulated by hydrocortisone spray during tillering phase, but its use for increasing grain productivity is limited. Similarly, spraying at grain filling phase did not

Effect of spraying hydrocortisone at different growth stages on yield, dry matter production, and harvest index per plot basis (16 m²).^a Pondicherry, India.

	Control	Active tillering (50 DAS)	Flowering (75 DAS)	Grain filling (100 DAS)	LSD (5%)
Yield (g)	9.10	10.21 (12)	11.00 (21)	10.30 (13)	1.16
Dry matter production (g)	21.81	26.38 (21)	25.58 (17)	24.70 (13)	4.04
Harvest index	0.41	0.39 (-6)	0.43 (4)	0.41 (-2)	ns

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase over control.

improve grain yield or dry matter production. To improve dry matter production and grain yield

simultaneously, a spray or hydrocortisone of 50 ppm at flowering stage is optimum. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Using a chlorophyll meter to predict need for topdressed nitrogen

F. T. Turner and M. F. Jund, Texas A&M Agriculture Research and Extension Center, Route 7 Box 999, Beaumont, Texas 77713, USA

Preliminary results show that a hand-held chlorophyll meter comes closer

than any other technique as a simple, quick, and accurate method for predicting the need to topdress N in semidwarf rice. A relationship between the chlorophyll content of the newest expanded leaf and the need for N fertilizer has been developed in 2 yr of experiments in research plots at Beaumont and in 1 yr at Bay City and Eagle Lake, Texas (see table).

We tested semidwarf Lemont variety